

Use of Zirconium Phosphate Column for the Separation of K^+ and Rb^+ Ions at Very Small Concentrations

D. K. BHATTACHARYYA and A. DE

Nuclear Chemistry Division, Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

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Radiochemical separation of very small quantities of potassium and rubidium has been achieved by passing an ice cold solution of their perchlorates through zirconium phosphate column. All ^{42}K activity elutes out when the column is washed with cold 10% perchloric acid. The retained ^{86}Rb activity has been later washed out with (1:1) HNO_3 . The β -decay study of ^{42}K activity and results of γ -spectrum analysis show that the separated products are of high radionuclidic purity. The overall separation procedure is clean, takes only 40 minutes and the yield is quantitative.

It has long been established that zirconium phosphate possesses remarkable ion exchange properties and the alkali metal cations could be reversibly exchanged¹ on this material. Separation of one alkali metal cation from another (in macro quantities) through the zirconium phosphate exchanger was achieved much earlier² on this basis. Besides its use as exchanger the stability of the H^+ -form of zirconium phosphate with respect to phosphate release was also determined in case of alkali metals, alkaline earths and other cations. This proved³ that the material possess⁴ appreciable capacity in both acid and alkaline medium, comparable to that of any typical cation exchange resin. Zirconium phosphate column was also utilised⁵ in the separation of some parent daughter radioisotope pairs such as $^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y$, $^{115}Cd - ^{115m}In$, $^{137}Cs - ^{137m}Ba$, $^{144}Ce - ^{144}Pr$ and $^{210}Pb - ^{210}Bi$. Present paper deals with the use of zirconium phosphate column for investigation of the modes of separation of potassium and rubidium from each other in very small, rather carrier free, concentration.

Several methods of both carrier and carrier free radiochemical analysis already exist for the separation of potassium from other alkali metal radionuclides. Most of these have been used to separate potassium radionuclides for use as radioactive tracer⁶ and for the determination of stable potassium by radioactivation analytical procedures^{7,8}. A carrier free method of determination of tracer potassium has also been reported in the analysis of alkali carbonates and chlorides⁹.

Besides several separation procedures for the alkali metal cations already mentioned in the literature, use of Dowex - 50^{10,11}, Amberlite IR - 100^{9,12}, Ir - 1 and Wofatit - KS as ion exchanger materials have been reported for the separation of mixtures of potassium and other alkali metal cations. In the present paper an attempt is made for the purpose of radiochemically separating potassium from rubidium at very small concentrations (5×10^{-6} g of Rb^+ and 2.5×10^{-6} g of K^+ ions) and to explore

the possibility of inclusion of other alkali metals as well, at similar concentrations, using zirconium phosphate column; and also to compare the results with those obtained by other methods of separation for the same cations.

^{42}K (12.4h) and ^{86}Rb (19.5d) are the two most frequently measured alkali metal radioisotopes available for easy counting techniques such as with Geiger-Mueller, Proportional or Gamma scintillation counting and hence chosen for the present study.

Experimental

^{42}K as KCl in dil. HCl (specific activity 105 mci/g K) and ^{86}Rb as RbCl in dil. HCl (specific activity 112 mci/g Rb) were supplied by BARC, Trombay, India. $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ was of Riedal variety and the metaphosphoric acid was of E. Merck quality. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Zirconium phosphate was prepared in the laboratory by mixing hot metaphosphoric acid solution in nitric acid with a solution of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ in 4N HCl added dropwise with constant stirring, temperature of the solution being maintained at 60°. Precipitation, washing, drying and analysis of the sample obtained were carried out in the way already described⁵. The ratio of zirconium : phosphate was found to be 1 : 2. The prepared solid was found to be very hard, stable in concentrated HNO_3 , HCl and in slightly alkaline solutions even on boiling. The granular material obtained was considered to be sufficiently stable for studies at ordinary temperature and found to be very suitable for column operation. This was grounded to fine powder and packed in a small glass column (6 × 0.5 cm) supported both at the top and the bottom by a little glass wool.

Measurement of activities : For counting of the β -activities a Philips G. M. type liquid counter (mica

window thickness 2.5-3.5 mg/cm² dia. 27.8 mm) was taken. An ECIL Ge(Li) detector of about 8 cm³ active volume and a leben 512-channel analyser were used to assay the γ -ray activities of ⁴²K and ⁸⁶Rb respectively. The system resolution was 6 keV at the 1032 keV γ -ray of ⁶⁰Co. The relative photopeak efficiency of the detector over the range of γ -rays investigated was also established using the relative γ -ray intensities of ⁶⁰Co and ⁵⁶Co to an accuracy better than 5%. Strong γ -ray sources were recorded in the same geometry as for the source to show the calibrating energies closely around the unknown photopeaks and thus the γ -ray energies were determined.

10 ml solutions (~7,000 c.p.m.) from each of the ⁴²K and ⁸⁶Rb activities were mixed together and the solution was evaporated to a volume of about 5 ml, cooled and kept surrounded by ice cold water for sometime. Perchloric acid (4 drops) was next added to it when no precipitation was observed. The solution was further cooled by ice cold water for a few minutes with occasional stirring and then poured over the zirconium phosphate column which was also kept cooled by passing ice cold water through the outer glass jacket. The washed out solution was collected in the receiver placed below and the column was washed with several small portions of 10% ice cold perchloric acid solution. The washings were collected and counted each time with the G. M. liquid counter. The nature of the β -decay half life of the activity present in the collected solution was recorded. The process was continued till the volume reached to 42 ml and the solution showed the presence of activity having half life most probably of ⁴²K. From the counting data an elution curve was also obtained (Fig. 1a) for ⁴²K.

Fig. 1. Elution curve of ⁴²K(1a) and ⁸⁶Rb(1b).

The experiment was then repeated with the mixture of ⁴²K and ⁸⁶Rb activities in the same proportions and treated with cold 10% HClO₄. The column was then connected to water pump by which the elution was regulated to the flow rate of 10-11 drops per minute and gradually washed with 42 ml ice cold 10% perchloric acid in small amounts. The washings were collected together. An aliquot of 10 ml from this was counted for ⁴²K activity and the nature of β -decay was studied (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Decay curve of ⁴²K separated from the mixture of ⁴²K and ⁸⁶Rb.

The experiments conducted so far indicated that some activity, presumably of ⁸⁶Rb adhered in the column. This was washed out with (1:1) hot nitric acid. An elution curve at this stage was obtained which showed that only 30 ml of nitric acid washed out the ⁸⁶Rb activity completely (Fig. 1b).

The solutions (30 ml) obtained here was then evaporated thrice with small quantity of water to remove the nitric acid as far as possible and finally taken with a little water followed by 1 ml of HClO₄. The mixture was heated to fumes, cooled and 50 mg of Rb in the form of RbCl was added. 1 ml of HClO₄ was then added dropwise with stirring. An instantaneous white crystalline precipitate was obtained. This was washed several times with ice cold absolute alcohol in a centrifuge, dried, mounted and examined for γ -spectrum (Fig. 3a).

In an identical chemical procedure a perchlorate, for both the ⁴²K and ⁸⁶Rb activities mixed together, was precipitated, processed and examined for γ -spectrum (Fig. 3b) for comparison with that obtained for Rb⁺ species, separated earlier.

Fig. 3. Gamma-spectrum obtained with a Ge(Li) detector of (a) the mixture of ^{42}K and ^{86}Rb before separation and (b) ^{86}Rb after separation from the mixture with ^{42}K . The energies marked are in MeV.

Discussion

A glance at the elution curve (Fig. 1a) showed that only 42 ml of 10% ice cooled HClO_4 was required to remove all the ^{42}K activity. It was found from preliminary studies that a more dilute HClO_4 required bigger volume and longer time. On the other hand a more concentrated form of HClO_4 washes out some ^{86}Rb activity and complicates the identification of the isotopes. A slow flow rate of 10-11 drops per min and a concentration of 10% HClO_4 in ice cold temperature proved to be the best for the washing of ^{42}K activity alone.

Due to the convenient half life of ^{42}K (12.4h) the β -decay of the solution for ^{42}K was studied. It is evident from the β -decay curve (Fig. 2) that the product ^{42}K , separating out from the zirconium phosphate column, is of a high radiochemical purity. The elution curve (Fig. 1b) shows that only 30 ml of (1 : 1) nitric acid is required for the

complete washing of the retained ^{86}Rb activity from ZrP column.

It is also evident from Fig. 3a that the ^{86}Rb , separated from ^{42}K , is of a high radionuclidic purity and ^{42}K did not interfere. The separate γ -ray spectrum taken for the original mixture solution containing both ^{42}K and ^{86}Rb is also placed (Fig. 3b) side by side for comparison.

Results of the experiments showed that when very cold perchloric acid passes through the column, it brings down only ^{42}K with it and ^{86}Rb in the perchlorate form remains preferentially adsorbed. It appears that this Rb^+ ion at very small (tracer) concentration probably assumed an insoluble character at the temperature of ice cold water and exchanged reversibly with the H^+ ion of ZrP material, similar to the properties exhibited in the studies on the alkali metal cations in macro concentrations by earlier workers¹. The mechanism of ion exchange with the replacable hydrogen ions of the ZrP material might have taken place here too. The difference of uptake observed for the two tracer cations under study was also found to be of similar nature when compared to the determination of affinity series of alkali metals^{1,3,14} by ZrP. The reason for this could be due to specific size effect which requires further study. The results of the above radiochemical separation indicated that the zirconium phosphate column can be well proposed for the separation of very small amounts of all alkali metals, and other similar cations as well, in suitable experimental conditions. The overall separation procedure takes only 40 minutes, is very clean and the yield is found to be quantitative.

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